

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

MITIGATION OF NURSE LEADER BURNOUT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Dawn Price

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Elizabeth J. Winokur, PhD, RN, CEN, Team Leader
Shauna K. Pearce, DNP, MAOM, RN, HACP, Team Member

May 2024

Author Note

Dawn Price - <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-5748-1819>
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13737699
© 2024 Dawn Price

ABSTRACT

Burnout is a substantial problem in healthcare and is identified as a significant cause of nurses leaving the nursing profession. Burnout for clinical nurses at the bedside is well researched, but there is a growing need to investigate burnout of nurse leaders. This project utilized the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI) self-report assessment survey, which measures burnout in the workplace, and the Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (PARIHS) conceptual framework to guide the implementation of an evidenced-based burnout mitigation toolkit for nurse leaders. The toolkit included a validated assessment tool, comprehensive education, and training based on the Institute of Health Improvement (IHI) “Framework for Improving Joy in Work” (2017), support tools, and workplace adjustments. Education sessions provided nurse leaders with the knowledge and skills to identify symptoms of burnout and effectively manage stress. Comparing results from the pre-and-post surveys demonstrates trending in the correct direction, indicating lower levels of burnout. The data indicates that nurse leaders are feeling varying degrees of mental and emotional exhaustion and disengagement. The results imply that burnout among nurse leaders may be influenced by various factors such as workload, organizational culture, and job demands. Additionally, findings indicate that aspects of their work, such as incorporating innovative practices, professional development opportunities, or engaging in meaningful projects, support nurse leader well-being and help to mitigate nurse leader burnout. Findings from this project demonstrate the presence of burnout among nurse leaders and promising results from the use of the mitigation of burnout toolkit.

Keywords: Nurse leaders, burnout, mitigation of leader burnout

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	vii
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	2
Purpose Statement.....	2
PICO Question.....	3
Project Objectives.....	3
Supporting Framework.....	3
Project Application PARIHS Framework.....	6
REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....	8
Overview.....	8
Search Strategy.....	8
Compassion Fatigue & Compassion Satisfaction.....	9
Why Nurse Leaders Leave Their Positions.....	11
The Effect of COVID-19 on Burnout.....	12
The Cost of Nurse Leader Burnout.....	13
Mitigation of Nurse Leader Burnout.....	14
Theoretical Framework.....	15
METHODS.....	16
Design.....	16
Setting.....	17
Measures.....	18
Procedure.....	20
Ethical Considerations.....	21
Data Collection and Analysis.....	22
RESULTS.....	23
Descriptive Statistics Pre-Post T-test.....	24
OLBI and Demographic Correlations.....	24
Exhaustion.....	25

Engagement.....	26
OLBI Combined Subscales.....	27
Qualitative Data Summary.....	28
Plan for Dissemination.....	28
DISCUSSION.....	29
Recommendations.....	32
Implications.....	33
Limitations.....	34
Conclusions.....	34
REFERENCES.....	36
APPENDIX A: Project Timeline.....	40
APPENDIX B: Evaluation Methods.....	41
APPENDIX C: PSJMC Nurse Satisfaction Data (October 2022).....	42
APPENDIX D: PSJMC Nurse Satisfaction Data (October 2023).....	43
APPENDIX E: PSJMC Patient Experience Data.....	44
APPENDIX F: Figure 1. PARIHS Framework.....	45
APPENDIX G: Figure 2. Modified PARIHS Framework.....	46
APPENDIX H: OLBI Survey Questionnaire.....	47
APPENDIX I: Table 1: Descriptive Statistics OLBI Pre and Post Mean Averages.....	51
APPENDIX J: Table 2: OLBI Subscales Pre-Post Survey 4-Point Scale.....	52
APPENDIX K: Table 3: Correlations Spearman's Rho OLBI Post Survey.....	54
APPENDIX L: Table 4: Participant Demographics.....	55
APPENDIX M: OLBI Survey Use Permission Request.....	56
APPENDIX N: Institutional DNP Project Approval Letter.....	57
APPENDIX O: Providence IRB Clinical Inquiry Project-Not Research Determination.....	58
APPENDIX P: California State University, Los Angeles IRB Approval Letter.....	59

APPENDIX Q: Western Institute of Nursing Conference Abstract60
CSULA 15th Annual Evidenced-Based Practice Nursing Forum Abstract.....60
CSUF Sigma Upsilon Beta International Induction Ceremony and Poster Session Abstract 60

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am deeply grateful to numerous individuals who have been instrumental in supporting me during my DNP journey and project. Firstly, I extend my heartfelt appreciation to my entire family. My parents and sisters who have always been there for me, and special gratitude to my husband John and our children Noah, Sarah, and Jonathan. Their unwavering encouragement and love have been invaluable throughout every phase of this endeavor. Words cannot fully convey the depth of my eternal gratitude for their support and patience.

I would also like to express my appreciation to Dr. Elizabeth J. Winokur, my team leader, whose dedication, and inspiration were pivotal during this program. Her exceptional leadership and guidance were indispensable, leading me through each step of the process with great care. Additionally, I extend my thanks to Dr. Shauna K. Pearce, my team mentor, for her constant kindness, expertise, and advice.

To my colleagues who participated in this project, I am profoundly thankful for your encouragement and support. Your involvement was essential, and without it, the completion of this project would not have been possible.

Furthermore, I extend my appreciation to the faculty of the Southern California CSU DNP Consortium for their persistence and understanding. Their assistance was essential to the successful completion of this work, and I am extremely thankful.

Background

Burnout is a significant problem in the United States (U.S.) and has a considerable role in why nurses are leaving the workforce or are considering leaving their professional nursing careers (Shah et al., 2021). Burnout is defined as a state of continuous psychological stress within work life and has been identified as having an influential negative impact on patients, the workforce, and organizations (Kelly & Adams, 2018). The Institute of Healthcare Improvement (IHI) reports that between 35%-54% of nurses in the U. S. have experienced significant symptoms of burnout (Perlo et al., 2017). The IHI states that nurse burnout can lead to decreased staff engagement, decreased productivity, lower patient experience scores, and increased workplace injury (Perlo et al., 2017). Burnout for clinical nurses at the bedside is well-studied, but there is a growing concern for the much less studied burnout of nurse leaders (Prochnow et al., 2021).

Nurse leaders are highly specialized and have an essential role within nursing practice. Elevated levels of stress, work demands, and lack of work-life balance result in distress that if not managed timely and appropriately, can cause burnout (Shah et al., 2021). Nurse leaders have added role responsibilities that lead to increased stress. Nurse leaders often carry the additional obligation of 24/7 department coverage, believing they must carry the burdens of their units, taking on projects or requests, and often working to support their teams at the bedside to cover severe nurse staff shortages (Kelly & Adams, 2018).

The IHI details three dimensions that are vital for the success of an organization's performance, including optimizing the patient experience, improving patient health, and reducing the cost of care (Nundy et al., 2022). Nurse leaders have a critical role in achieving all of these aims for success, and there is a significant impact due to burnout of nurse leaders on each aim

and the ability of organizations to optimize these aims (Prochnow et al., 2021). There is limited research on the cost connected with nurse leader turnover, but the loss of a registered nurse leaving their position is associated with a significant fiscal impact, estimated between \$11,000 to \$90,000 per nurse, averaging about \$50,000 per nurse, with up to \$8.5 million in associated wider costs (Kelly et al., 2021). The turnover of nurse leaders in an organization not only impacts direct costs but additionally impacts indirect costs such as decreased quality, patient satisfaction, and caregiver experience, as well as the financial implications of having to recruit and retrain new nurse leaders to fill vacated positions (Kelly & Adams, 2018). Shortage of qualified nurses to fill vacant nurse leadership positions in hospitals within the U. S causes stress on organizations, patient care departments, and staff.

Problem Statement

Burnout continues to be reported by registered nurses across a variety of practice settings and at all levels of nursing nationwide (Kelly & Adams, 2018). The challenges in the current healthcare work environment create conditions for professional burnout at all nursing levels, including nurse leaders (Kelly et al., 2021).

Project Purpose

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to create a nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit based on the Institute of Health Improvement (IHI) “Framework for Improving Joy in Work,” (2017) and conduct a pre-and post-toolkit implementation burnout assessment survey at a community, Magnet[®]-recognized acute care hospital. The goal of this project was to determine the efficacy of the toolkit in decreasing nurse leader burnout.

PICO Question

Population: A nurse leader for this project is defined as a registered nurse in the role of a supervisor, manager, director, executive director, or administrator who a) currently holds a nurse leader role and b) spends the majority of their time (>51%) in leadership activities.

Intervention: Create and implement a nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit.

Comparison: Conduct a pre-and post-toolkit implementation burnout assessment survey.

Outcome: To decrease nurse leader burnout with the implementation of a nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit.

Project Objectives

The overarching objective of this evidenced-based project is to mitigate nurse leader burnout with the implementation of a nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit. An additional aim was to estimate the direct and indirect impact of nurse leader burnout on nurse leader turnover, nurse satisfaction, and patient experience.

Supporting Framework

Multiple factors are associated with limiting quality research from being translated into clinical practice, including poor quality of evidence, communication issues, logistical barriers, dissemination challenges, financial constraints, and resistance to change (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). As well, it can be difficult to translate research into an actual practice change because of factors related to barriers in the local healthcare setting. These include the complexity of the healthcare system, the need to consider multiple stakeholders, the necessity to account for variation in practice context, difficulties measuring outcomes, and the complexity of changing existing practices and behaviors (Helfrich et al., 2010). Understanding and addressing these factors can help to ensure that research is implemented and that evidence-based practices (EBP)

are adopted. A conceptual framework can be utilized to help guide and structure the implementation process of EBP change. It provides a clear understanding of the key elements associated with successful implementation and provides a framework for organizing and understanding the application process.

A conceptual framework can identify potential barriers as well as measure and evaluate the effectiveness of the implementation process. It can ensure that all relevant stakeholders understand the EBP change and are committed to its success (Sandström et al., 2011). The Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (PARIHS) framework identifies the necessary key elements that influence the success of a practice change. This DNP project utilized the PARIHS model for evidence-based implementation to facilitate the adoption of a nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit with a project goal of lessening nurse leader burnout.

The PARIHS framework is a model for understanding and promoting the successful implementation of EBP in healthcare settings. It was developed in the early 1990s by a team of international researchers in the United Kingdom (Harvey & Kitson, 2016) and is based on the premise that successful implementation of research evidence into practice is a complex process that involves a combination of evidence, context, and facilitation (Bergström et al., 2020). The framework was created in response to the growing recognition that evidence-based healthcare has immense potential to improve the quality of care, but that in practice, this potential is not consistently realized. The PARIHS team undertook a review of the literature to identify the core elements that influence the successful execution of research evidence into practice, and then developed the framework components to provide evidence-based guidance on how to effectively implement research findings into healthcare settings (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). It offers a conceptual framework for understanding the factors that influence the implementation of EBP.

The PARIHS framework focuses on three core components: evidence, context, and facilitation. The first component of the framework is based on the concept of evidence-based healthcare, which is the process of using the best available evidence to make decisions about healthcare interventions. Evidence is broadly defined as any information or data that is used to assess the effectiveness of an intervention or to inform decisions about healthcare. This includes clinical trials, observational studies, systematic reviews, economic analyses, and expert opinion (Bergström et al., 2020). An example of evidence that could be used to assess the effectiveness of a particular intervention using the PARIHS framework would be a systematic review of clinical trials that examined the effects of an intervention on patient outcomes. This provides information on the effectiveness of the intervention, as well as any potential harm associated with it.

The second component, context, looks at the environment in which the intervention is provided, including the setting, resources, personnel, and other factors that can influence the outcome. This component considers any potential confounding factors that may affect the outcome, such as the availability of resources, the expertise of the personnel, and other contextual factors that could potentially affect the results. This component also looks at any probable ethical considerations that may arise when providing an intervention (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). An example of the PARIHS framework context would be the evaluation of a particular intervention. In this case, the context would include the setting where the intervention was implemented, such as a hospital or clinic. It would also include the resources available, such as equipment and staff, and any potential ethical considerations that may arise when providing the intervention. Additionally, the context would also review any prospective confounding factors,

such as the level of knowledge of the stakeholders and any other factors that could affect the outcome (Bergström et al., 2020).

The PARIHS framework's last component of facilitation addresses the aspect of how the EBP change is supported and facilitated. This includes activities such as educating healthcare professionals on the importance of EBP, creating policies and procedures to support evidence-based decision-making, and providing resources and support to enable healthcare providers to access and use the best available evidence to inform their decisions. This component also looks at enacting action plans that involve collaboration between healthcare professionals, patients, and other stakeholders (Harvey et al., 2018). An example of the PARIHS framework component facilitation would be implementing a policy or procedure that requires providers to use the best available evidence to implement their decisions. This includes activities such as providing education on the importance of EBP, creating resources to support the use of evidence-based decision-making, and setting up systems to track and monitor results (Harvey et al., 2018) (Appendix F).

Project Application PARIHS Framework

The core PARIHS framework model elements can be further described as dynamic components that affect the likelihood of success in the implementation process of this practice change project, the primary key elements of evidence, context, and facilitation were adapted for this project (Appendix G).

Evidence includes the strength and quality of the evidence, the type of research designs used, and the extent of evidence-based knowledge. For this project, there is limited research regarding the burnout of nurse leaders and its overall effects on an organization (Prochnow et al.,

2021). There is, however, an abundance of evidence that burnout mitigation programs support nurses at all levels (Lisle et al., 2020).

Context refers to the external environment, such as organizational culture, organizational climate, engagement, and environments. For this project, the organizational and learning culture of the hospital encouraged the implementation of this burnout mitigation toolkit to decrease burnout and ensure the success of nurse leaders. The organization is a Magnet®-recognized hospital, and the administrative leaders supported the need for adequate resources for nurse leaders, not only to ensure their success in the nurse leader role, but to mitigate burnout and ultimately decrease the potential for nurse leader turnover.

Facilitation includes the strategies, processes, and activities that reinforce the implementation of EBP. The role of the facilitator is that of change agent that possesses the skills to communicate effectively and the ability to implement a practice change. For this project, as the facilitator, the project lead worked with the nurse leadership team, provided overall organization to the project, and led the implementation of a nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit as well as conducted a pre-and-post burnout assessment survey with a project goal to reduce nurse leader burnout.

Review of Literature

A literature review is needed to implement an EBP change because it provides an understanding of the current state of evidence in a field. It can help practitioners identify practice changes that have been successful in other settings, review the potential risks associated with the change, and determine if the practice is appropriate for their setting (Grove & Gray, 2019). It can also help to identify gaps in the existing literature and identify opportunities for further study. Additionally, a review of the literature can help practitioners identify potential barriers to the implementation of EBP in their organizational environment.

Search Strategy

A literature search was completed using the electronic databases CINAHL, PubMed, and APA PsycINFO. Key search terms included “nurse manager” or “nurse leader” and “burnout” or “turnover” and the search criteria included peer-reviewed research articles within the last five years. The initial search resulted in 68 articles. The search was narrowed to the terms “nurse leader” and “burnout,” yielding 52 results. Upon thorough review of these articles, many of the research studies were excluded because the studies focused on burnout of frontline nurses or direct clinical care nursing staff and how the nurse leader’s or manager’s style of leadership could impact and effect their burnout. Six studies were included that specifically addressed nurse leader burnout (Kelly et al., 2019; Lisle et al., 2020; Peacock, 2023; Prochnow et al., 2021; Remegio et al., 2021; Seguin, 2019).

All six of the studies are level IV observational, cross-sectional studies. Cross-sectional observational studies are used to determine prevalence at a single point in time (Bootland et al., 2017). They are relatively limited in scope and do not permit a distinction between cause and

effect. Levels of evidence are assigned to studies based on the quality of their design, validity, and application to patient care.

Level IV evidence is defined as the fourth highest and includes cross-sectional, mixed-method research, and qualitative meta-synthesis (Grove & Gray, 2019). Two of the studies are mixed method studies utilizing both quantitative and qualitative methods (Kelly et al., 2019; Prochnow et al., 2021). Mixed-method research is an approach to inquiry combining quantitative and qualitative research methods into a single study (Grove & Gray, 2019).

In the literature review for this DNP project, themes and contributing factors emerged around nurse leader burnout. The themes included the correlation between compassion fatigue and compassion satisfaction, why nurse leaders leave their positions, the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic, the cost of nurse leader burnout, and recommendations as to what needs to occur to mitigate nurse leader burnout.

Compassion Fatigue & Compassion Satisfaction

For this section of the literature review, a search was conducted utilizing PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. Search terms included nurse leader burnout, compassion fatigue, and compassion satisfaction. Three studies reported a significant increase in compassion fatigue scores for nurse leaders (Kelly et al., 2019; Lisle et al., 2020; Peacock, 2023). In addition, the Lisle et al. (2020) study identified compassion satisfaction themes of work satisfaction and a positive work environment. Four of the studies utilized the Professional Quality of Life (ProQOL) assessment, this validated survey tool measures compassion satisfaction (CS) and, indirectly, compassion fatigue (CF), which is comprised of burnout and secondary traumatic stress (STS) (Kelly et al., 2019; Lisle et al., 2020; Peacock, 2023; Remegio et al., 2021). The other two studies used the Maslach Burnout Inventory–Human Services Survey (MBI-HSS), a

validated psychological assessment tool that includes twenty-two symptom items relating to occupational burnout. In addition, the Seguin, 2019 study utilized the validated Short Grit scale (Grit-S) measurement tool. The Grit-S tool measures the extent to which individuals can maintain focus and interest and persevere in obtaining and reaching long-term goals. This study noted that the overall MBI-HSS score did not differ significantly between those with and without advanced degrees and identified grit as a desirable characteristic and a potential predictor of long-term nurse leader success. The two mixed method studies that included a qualitative component resulted in similar themes, including emotional drain, every interaction tells a story, managing psychological capital, and the work-life balance juggle (WLBJ) (Kelly et al., 2019; Lisle et al., 2020).

Strengths of the studies include the use of validated burnout assessment tools, the ProQOL and the MBI-HSS. There are a variety of validated tools to measure nurse burnout, including the MBI-HSS, the Nursing Stress Scale, the ProQOL, the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI), and the Nursing Resilience Scale. The MBI-HSS is a 22-item questionnaire designed to measure the three dimensions of burnout: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment (Prochnow et al., 2021; Seguin, 2019). The Nursing Stress Scale is a 16-item questionnaire designed to measure the levels of stress experienced by nurses. The ProQOL is a 30-item questionnaire designed to measure the quality of life experienced by nurses (Kelly et al., 2019; Lisle et al., 2020; Remegio et al., 2021). The OLBI is a 16-item, self-report assessment survey questionnaire designed to measure burnout in the workplace. The survey measures physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion experienced and levels of engagement in relation to work (Pate et al., 2023). The Nursing Resilience Scale is a 20-item questionnaire designed to measure levels of resilience experienced by nurses (Seguin, 2019).

The mixed method study by Kelly et al. (2019) identified that nurse leaders with greater experience reported less burnout and reported a significant increase in CF scores. The qualitative portion of the study noted similar themes, including emotional drain and WLBJ (Kelly et al., 2019). Two of the articles found that nurse leaders with greater experience reported less burnout (Kelly et al., 2019; Seguin, 2019).

These study results offer insights for healthcare and professional organizations about nurse leader burnout and the need to provide support for nurse leaders in their challenging work settings to prevent burnout. Nurse leaders must find compassion satisfaction from various sources, including peer and staff interactions, to mitigate the risk of burnout (Kelly et al., 2019). This theme of the literature review demonstrates the significance of CF and CS and their impact on nurse leader burnout that needs to be addressed to prevent the next theme discussed, why nurse leaders leave their positions.

Why Nurse Leaders Leave Their Positions

For this topic of the literature review section, searches were carried out using PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. Search terms included nurse leader burnout and nurse leader turnover. Nurse leaders can burn out and leave an organization for a variety of reasons, such as being overwhelmed by the demands of the job, feeling unsupported or undervalued, and experiencing a lack of job satisfaction (Seguin, 2019). Other contributing factors include inadequate staffing, lack of resources, and insufficient compensation (Lisle et al., 2020). Burnout contributing to nurse leader turnover can also be correlated with a lack of recognition and appreciation, autonomy and control, and professional development opportunities (Kelly et al., 2019; Lisle et al., 2020). Inadequate support from senior leaders was also noted as a potential impact on nurse leaders to feel undervalued and unsupported, leading to burnout and turnover

(Kelly et al., 2019). A poor work-life balance can cause nurse leaders to feel overworked and underpaid, leading to feelings of being unappreciated and taken for granted or undervalued, contributing to them seeking other opportunities (Kelly et al., 2019; Lisle et al., 2020; Peacock, 2023; Seguin, 2019).

Nurse leaders may become frustrated when roles and responsibilities are not clearly outlined or when role expectations are unclear (Kelly et al., 2019; Seguin, 2019). When nurse leaders are faced with leading overcrowded units, inadequate resources, and outdated equipment, they may feel unmotivated and seek other opportunities. Lastly, when nurse leaders do not feel connected to their team or workplace, they may be less productive and may eventually look for other opportunities. These contributing factors to nurse leader turnover are well documented, while the theme of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on burnout is just beginning to be studied.

The Effect of COVID-19 on Burnout

For this theme of the literature review, a search was conducted utilizing PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. The search terms included nurse leader burnout and the novel coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. The Great Resignation is a term used to describe the unprecedented exodus of nurses from their profession due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. One study estimated that more than one million nurses in the U.S. will leave the profession in the next two years due to burnout related to the pandemic (Boston-Fleischhauer, 2022). The pandemic took an extreme toll on nurses, due to long hours, grueling shifts, and the emotional and physical toll of caring for COVID-19 patients. It also placed an enormous strain on nurse leaders, who had to make complex decisions and manage unprecedented levels of stress and uncertainty. This has led to a dramatic increase in nurse leader

burnout, with many experiencing feelings of being overwhelmed and exhausted by the pressure and responsibility (Peacock, 2023). As a result, nurse leaders have decided to leave the profession, contributing to the Great Resignation. Two of the articles are from 2019, before the COVID-19 worldwide pandemic (Kelly et al., 2019; Seguin, 2019), and four were completed after the start of the COVID-19 pandemic (Lisle et al., 2020; Peacock, 2023; Prochnow et al., 2021), although one of the studies completed after the start of the pandemic notes that the assessments were completed prior and did not address the potential effects of COVID-19 (Remegio et al., 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic has potentially had a significant impact on the previous problem of nurse leader burnout. The Prochnow (2021) study addressed the COVID-19 pandemic and the potential impact on nurse leader burnout. This study also garnered the fewest positive results for nurse leaders in work-life balance and resource allocation (Prochnow et al., 2021). The Peacock (2023) study was completed at two separate survey intervals, first in the fall of 2019 and second in the spring of 2021 post-COVID-19 pandemic, 13 months after it was declared a global pandemic. The other four studies did not discuss study results in correlation to the COVID-19 pandemic (Kelly et al., 2019; Lisle et al., 2020; Remegio et al., 2021; Seguin, 2019). More research is needed to truly know the direct impact of COVID-19 on nurse burnout at all levels and the actual cost of nurse leader burnout to healthcare overall.

The Cost of Nurse Leader Burnout

For this segment of the literature review, a search was conducted utilizing PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. Search terms included nurse burnout cost and nurse leader turnover financial cost. The healthcare cost implications of nurse leader burnout include decreased patient satisfaction, increased costs for recruitment and training, decreased quality of care, and an increased risk of medical errors (Nundy et al., 2022). Data specific to the monetary

costs associated with the loss of nurse leaders was not found. However, nurse leaders have been included in the estimates of the financial implications of nursing turnover. The turnover cost per nurse averages about \$50,000 per nurse, with up to \$8.5 million in associated wider costs (Kelly et al., 2021). High nurse leader turnover can also lead to an increase in overtime costs and a decrease in overall productivity. Burnout can also lead to an increase in staff absenteeism, which can result in a decrease in staff productivity through increasing the staff-to-patient ratio or decreasing the number of patients seen, all often resulting in decreased patient satisfaction. The monetary cost implications of nurse leader turnover include costs associated with hiring and training inexperienced staff, as well as costs associated with decreased productivity and quality of care (Kelly et al., 2021). Additionally, when nurse leaders leave, their knowledge and experience can be difficult to replace, which can lead to an increase in costs associated with mentoring and training new staff. Finally, high nurse leader turnover can lead to decreased staff morale and an increase in staff absenteeism, which can further add to the costs of turnover (Perlo et al., 2017). Peer support, education, and burnout mitigation programs for nurse leaders should not be lost among an organization's competing priorities.

Mitigation of Nurse Leader Burnout

For this section of the literature review, a search was conducted utilizing PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. Search terms included mitigation of nurse leader burnout and nurse burnout mitigation. As discussed, it is imperative to mitigate nurse leader burnout because it can have a negative impact on patient safety and quality of care. Burnout can lead to decreased job satisfaction and morale, increased turnover, and decreased productivity (Peacock, 2023). Mitigating burnout can help to ensure that nurse leaders have the energy, focus, and motivation to provide high-quality care and be supportive of their staff. Burnout mitigation tools can include

providing more resources and support, offering flexible scheduling and professional development opportunities, and implementing an effective recognition and rewards program (Peacock, 2023; Remegio et al., 2021). Additionally, creating an inclusive and positive workplace culture, providing regular feedback, and coaching, and encouraging healthy work-life balance can all help mitigate burnout and reduce turnover (Prochnow et al., 2021).

Theoretical Framework

For the theoretical framework portion of the literature review, a search utilizing CINAHL and Google Scholar included the PARIHS framework and how to utilize it in the implementation of evidence in nursing. Search terms included PARHIS framework, application, implementation, and nurse leader burnout. The PARIHS framework is a tool used to identify and understand the key factors that influence the successful implementation of EBP change. The search did not locate studies that used the PARIHS model specifically regarding the subject of nurse leader burnout; there was a similar study that identified the use of the PARIHS model in the type of leader, including leader characteristics (Sandström et al., 2011). The findings indicated that nursing leadership is vital for the process of implementing EBP in nursing. Nurse leaders identify the necessary components of successful practice change programs and provide a structured approach for understanding and implementing practice change initiatives. The role of the nurse leader helps organizations focus on the key components of successful practice change and is critical to guiding how to implement EBP successfully (Sandström et al, 2011). In conclusion, although there are limited studies utilizing the PARHIS framework referencing nurse leader burnout, for this project, the PARIHS framework will provide guidance to ensure the success of the project implementation.

Methods

The methods section of this DNP project will detail utilizing a toolkit designed to mitigate burnout among nurse leaders. Developed in accordance with the IHI's "Framework for Improving Joy in Work," (2017) this toolkit aims to diminish burnout levels among nurse leaders. In October 2022, Providence St Jude Medical Center (PSJMC) registered its lowest burnout score on the Willis Tower Watson (WTW) nurse satisfaction survey, standing at 38%, indicating a 4% decrease compared to the preceding year (Appendix C). Furthermore, the survey results in October 2023 indicated continued burnout and results declined an additional 1% to 37%, remaining the lowest scoring measure of the entire survey (Appendix D).

Design

This DNP project utilized the PARIHS conceptual framework to direct the implementation of an evidence-based toolkit designed to mitigate burnout among nurse leaders, drawing inspiration from the IHI's "Framework for Improving Joy in Work" (2017). The toolkit encompassed various elements including a validated assessment tool, thorough education and training, support resources, workplace adjustments, and evaluation methods (Shanafelt & Noseworthy, 2017). The IHI's framework addresses the pressing issue of burnout and dissatisfaction among healthcare professionals, highlighting the pivotal role of healthcare workers' well-being in ensuring high-quality patient care. Core components of the framework comprise organizational support, efficiency of work processes, relational coordination, and meaning in work (Perlo et al., 2017).

The validated OLBI burnout assessment questionnaire was utilized to gauge nurse leader burnout by assessing mental, physical, and emotional exhaustion and engagement. Education and training were provided to equip nurse leaders with the necessary skills to effectively manage

stress, while a list of available support systems was furnished, including information on wellness programs like Lyra, a list of wellness resources, and the organization's wellness activity schedules. The toolkit encompassed a range of well-being tools such as Press Pause cards, aromatherapy, reflection books, wearable wellness patches, notebooks, and acupuncture rings, each serving to alleviate stress and promote well-being in distinct ways.

The Press Pause cards served as gentle reminders to take mindful breaks, fostering mental reset and rejuvenation. Aromatherapy inhalers, featuring essential oils known for their stress-relieving properties, were incorporated to create a soothing environment. Reflection books facilitated self-reflection, aiding in burnout management by promoting self-awareness and resilience. Notebooks provided a space for organizing thoughts and tasks, while wellness patches delivered targeted benefits for stress relief and mood enhancement. Acupressure rings target specific pressure points to alleviate tension.

Furthermore, the toolkit included a list of available resources, such as mental health services and support groups, to foster a sense of community and support. By incorporating these well-being tools into daily routines, individuals could proactively manage stress and prevent burnout, ultimately cultivating resilience. Each participant received a toolkit and education on the components of the toolkit. Finally, comprehensive data analysis and evaluation were conducted to assess the toolkit's effectiveness, with workplace adjustments planned based on survey results to mitigate sources of nurse leader burnout.

Setting

This DNP project was implemented at Providence PSJMC, a community hospital providing acute care services located in Fullerton, California. PSJMC operates as a 320-bed, non-profit hospital and holds Magnet®-recognition designation, featuring a staff of nearly 700

physicians and approximately 1000 employed nurses. The project team comprises of the DNP student acting as the facilitator, the DNP project chair, and the organization's nurse leaders.

Measures

This DNP project used the OLBI self-administered, validated assessment tool intended to gauge workplace burnout, evaluating physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion as well as the level of engagement associated with work (Pate et al., 2023). Its purpose is to determine the severity and breadth of burnout symptoms.

The OLBI comprises 16 items that participants rate on a 4 or 5-point Likert scale, spanning from 1 to 5 (Demerouti & Bakker, 2008). These questions target three dimensions of burnout: emotional exhaustion, engagement, and lack of personal accomplishment. Additionally, the survey includes inquiries regarding the respondent's current job situation, the level of stress experienced at work, and overall job satisfaction (Demerouti et al., 2010). This survey is widely applicable across various work environments, particularly in healthcare. Its outcomes aim to furnish insights into an individual's burnout level and can assist in guiding interventions and assessing their efficacy. Previous research has established the OLBI's sound reliability and validity (Demerouti & Bakker, 2008), rendering it a commonly employed tool for assessing burnout across diverse work settings. In this project, the OLBI was employed to conduct pre-and post-toolkit implementation burnout surveys (Appendix H).

The OLBI survey 16 items are divided between two subscales, the items are also summed to form two sub-totals: disengagement items: 1, 3, 6, 7, 9, 11, 13, and 15; exhaustion items: 2, 4, 5, 8, 10, 12, 14 and 16. Survey items 1, 5, 7, 10, 13, 14, 15, and 16 were scored as follows: Strongly agree (1); agree (2); neither agree nor disagree (3); disagree (4); strongly disagree (5). For items 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 11, and 12, the scale is reversed, with strongly agree answers scoring

(5) and strongly disagree answers scoring (1). The four-point scale removes neither agree nor disagree items. Similarly, demographic questions were included as follows: how long you have been in a leadership role, what is highest level of education completed and are you certified as a nurse leader. Two additional qualitative questions were included in the post-survey. “Please identify one tool, if any, that you found most beneficial from the mitigation of nurse leader burnout toolkit provided” and “please identify the most beneficial information, if any, provided in the mitigation of nurse leader burnout education sessions”.

The WTW survey serves as an employee engagement survey tool aimed at assessing employee engagement within the workplace. This survey gathers data on various aspects such as job satisfaction, work-life balance, career advancement opportunities, communication effectiveness, trust levels, and motivational factors (Danaci & Koc, 2020). Furthermore, it evaluates the overall workplace atmosphere and culture. Its primary objective is to furnish employers with insights into their employees' sentiments regarding their work and organizational affiliation, aiding in the identification of areas necessitating enhancement (Danaci & Koc, 2020). A baseline survey conducted at PSJMC in October 2022 revealed notable levels of burnout among nurses across all hierarchies (Appendix C).

The intention of the project was to contrast these findings with post-implementation data following the introduction of the nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit. By comprehending employees' sentiments and perceptions, employers can make informed decisions aimed at enhancing the workplace environment and fostering greater support and engagement among their workforces.

Press Ganey Patient Experience surveys are tools used to gather feedback from patients about their healthcare experiences. These surveys typically cover various aspects of the patient

journey, including interactions with healthcare providers, the quality of medical care received, communication with staff, wait times, facility cleanliness, and overall satisfaction with the healthcare encounter (Howell et al., 2020). These surveys are essential for healthcare organizations as they provide valuable insights into patient perspectives, allowing them to identify areas of strength and areas needing improvement. In February 2023, PSJMC's overall patient experience score was 71.14% (Appendix E).

By analyzing the feedback collected through Press Ganey surveys, healthcare providers can implement changes to enhance patient satisfaction, improve the quality of care, and ultimately, positively impact patient outcomes. Nurse leader burnout can contribute to lower patient experience scores by undermining the quality of care and interpersonal interactions within healthcare settings. Addressing nurse leader burnout is crucial for improving patient experience and ensuring the delivery of high-quality care (Peacock, 2023). The intention is to contrast these findings with post-implementation data following the introduction of the nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit.

Procedure

Prior to the initiation of the burnout mitigation toolkit, the OLBI burnout assessment pre-survey was distributed via email to nurse leaders who were a registered nurse in the role of a supervisor, manager, director, executive director, or administrator who currently hold a nurse leader role and spends the majority of their time in leadership activities. The email invitations were sent out using the nurse leaders' work email addresses obtained from the PSJMC nurse leader Outlook distribution list. Each email contained a request to participate in the project. Additionally, an informational cover sheet was included with the email, offering supplementary details about the survey process. This informational sheet, along with a link to the Microsoft

Forms survey, was distributed electronically, with no collection of email addresses. Subsequent reminder emails were sent on a weekly basis over a span of three weeks to encourage completion of the OLBI pre-assessment survey. Utilizing Microsoft Forms, the survey was conducted to collect participant responses. One week after the completion of the pre-survey assessment, the burnout mitigation toolkit was introduced.

To educate participants about the toolkit, informational education sessions were arranged. These sessions were conducted to provide education, insights, and guidance on utilizing the mitigation of burnout toolkit effectively. Flexibility was offered by scheduling the information sessions three times, allowing participants to select the most suitable date and time to attend. Notification of the meeting timings and proposed agenda was conveyed to the nurse leaders through email and Outlook invites.

The post-survey was administered 45 days following the deployment of the toolkit and the conclusion of the final education session. Subsequent reminder emails were sent on a weekly basis over a span of three weeks to encourage completion of the OLBI post-assessment survey. In addition to the same items covered in the pre-survey, two additional questions pertaining to the usefulness of the toolkit and education information were included in the post-survey assessment.

Ethical Considerations

The project lead successfully completed training through the Collaborative Institutional Training Initiative and obtained a certificate from the Human Research Protection Program. Prior to commencing the DNP project, a letter of approval for the project was obtained from the hospital's Chief Nursing Officer (Appendix N). Additionally, approval was granted by the Providence Institutional Review Board (IRB) (Appendix O) and the IRB from California State

University, Los Angeles (CSULA) (Appendix P). Throughout the project, utmost attention was given to maintaining participant confidentiality, with no collection of identifiable information. The burnout assessment survey data remained anonymous, as no email addresses or names were solicited or recorded, ensuring the anonymity of the data results. Data storage occurred on a password-protected computer to safeguard participant information. Only de-identified data was collected, and data was reported in aggregate to preserve participant privacy and confidentiality.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data from the pre-and -post assessment survey was exported into an Excel spreadsheet and imported into Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28 for analysis. Non-parametric statistics were used to describe the sample and identify the degree of burnout and exhaustion. Parametric statistics were used to measure the relationship between two or more variables by analyzing the differences in their means or variances. This type of statistical analysis allows researchers to identify relationships between variables and determine the impact that one variable has on another (Grove & Gray, 2019). By understanding the relationship between variables, more informed decisions about how to best address the problem or phenomenon of nurse leader burnout.

Results

The sample included a total of 25 qualified nurse leaders, of whom 24 took part in the pre-survey, representing a participation rate of 96% of eligible nurse leaders. While 24 nurse leaders completed the education sessions, one leader resigned during the project. Subsequently, 22 nurse leaders completed the post-survey out of the remaining 24, accounting for a 92% completion rate. The participant demographics included nurse leaders with the number of years of experience in the role ranging from 1 to 20+ years and a combination of both BSN (6) and MSN or higher (18) prepared (Appendix L).

This DNP project utilized numerical coding to prepare data for analysis in SPSS version 28. The OLBI survey 16 items were divided between two subscales, the items were also summed to form two sub-totals: disengagement and exhaustion items. Participants rate on either a 4 or 5-point Likert like scale; for this project, the initial questionnaire utilized a 5-point Likert scale. For comparison with some reference studies, the score was converted to the four-point scale (Demerouti & Bakker, 2008). Additionally, demographic data, like "How many years have you been in a nurse leader position," were divided into categories and assigned numerical coding, ranging from 1 for 1-5 years to 5 for 20+ years. All survey information underwent numerical coding for consistency. Two additional qualitative questions were included in the post-survey. "Please identify one tool, if any, that you found most beneficial from the mitigation of nurse leader burnout toolkit provided" and "please identify the most beneficial information, if any, provided in the mitigation of nurse leader burnout education sessions." Themes were identified through the collection and evaluation of related responses. A thorough analysis and assessment of data were undertaken to gauge the efficacy of the toolkit. The project lead computed the effect

size; however, given the small sample size, the interpretation process leaned on the p-value approach to ascertain statistical significance (Grove & Gray, 2019).

Descriptive Statistics Pre-Post T-test

The t-test results for the OLBI pre-post questionnaire revealed statistical significance in the following question: "This is the only type of work I can imagine myself doing" demonstrating a significant difference between the pre-and-post project implementation mean ($p = .031$). A few additional questions demonstrated trending in a positive direction and approached statistical significance. "After working, I have enough energy for my leisure activities" ($p = .091$), "I feel more and more engaged in my work" ($p = .106$), and "I find my work to be a positive challenge" ($p = .117$). The remainder of the survey questions before and after the intervention indicated a positive trend but did not yield statistically significant results. (Appendix D). Correlations were computed between various variables to assist in identifying specific areas requiring further interventions. Then, important associations were divided into demographic, and two subscale categories the OLBI survey assesses, exhaustion and engagement.

OLBI and Demographic Correlations

Spearman's rho correlations were calculated for years of nursing experience and the highest level of degree completed and items on the scale. The results revealed a statistically significant relationship between the duration of years in a nurse leader position and the tendency to think less at work and perform tasks mechanically, ($r_s(38.77) = .429, p = .046$), indicating a positive association between years in a nurse leader position and decreased cognitive engagement at work. Conversely, the correlation coefficient between the highest level of degree completed and the tendency to think less at work and perform tasks mechanically was not

significant, ($r_s(38.77) = -.082, p = .718$), suggesting no substantial link between educational attainment and cognitive engagement at work.

Furthermore, an analysis was conducted to explore the connection between the number of years one has been a nurse leader and the ability to manage work effectively. The findings revealed a low to moderate positive correlation, ($r_s(38.77) = .388, p = .075$). Additionally, the correlation coefficient between the duration of years in a nurse leader position and the increasing sense of engagement in work was ($r_s(38.77) = 0.304, p = 0.168$), indicating a low to moderate relationship between tenure of nurse leaders and work engagement (Appendix K).

Exhaustion

The questions related to exhaustion in the OLBI survey are designed to assess feelings of physical, mental, and emotional depletion experienced by individuals in the context of their work. These questions aim to capture the extent to which individuals feel drained and overwhelmed by their job demands (Demerouti, et al., 2010). Nonparametric correlations, specifically Spearman's rho, were calculated for question pairs. A significant correlation was found in the questions "after work I need more time than in the past to relax and feel better" and "I talk about my work in a negative way" ($r_s(38.77) = .456, p = .025$), as well as with "tolerate the pressures of work" ($r_s(38.77) = -.502, p = .013$). In addition, the most significant correlation noted was in the exhaustion question, "During my work, I feel emotionally drained" and "I talk about my work in a negative way" ($r_s(37.88) = .761, p < .001$). Moreover, a moderate correlation ($r_s(38.77) = .472, p = .02$) was observed between feeling "worn out and weary after work" and "imagining myself only doing this work," indicating a moderately strong link between post-work exhaustion and envisioning exclusive engagement in that type of work in the future. In all instances, the p-values confirm the statistical significance of these correlations. In the exhaustion

subscale of the OLBI, higher scores indicate a higher level of exhaustion from work. The pre-intervention exhaustion score of 19.63 indicates low levels of exhaustion from the participants. The noted decrease in the exhaustion scores post-intervention, from 19.63 to 18.50, suggests a reduction in the reported level of exhaustion experienced by participants. This reduction is generally considered positive, as it indicates that the intervention may have helped participants feel less emotionally drained and exhausted by their work (Appendix J).

Engagement

The questions related to engagement in the OLBI are designed to assess individuals' level of involvement, enthusiasm, and connection to their work. These questions aim to capture the extent to which individuals feel connected, absorbed, and energized by their job responsibilities. Each question in the engagement category taps into different aspects of this experience, such as feeling understanding toward others, being able to detach from work, or maintaining a sense of humor despite job demands (Demerouti, et al., 2010). Significant correlations were identified between the engagement question "Lately, I tend to think less at work and do my job almost mechanically" and "Overtime, one can become disconnected from this type of work" ($r(38.77) = .413, p = .045$). Similarly, the statement "this is the only type of work I can imagine myself doing" and "sometimes I feel sickened by work tasks" yielded a correlation of ($r(38.77) = -.418, p = .042$).

Analysis also revealed a significant positive relationship between "I always find new and interesting aspects of my work" and "I can tolerate the pressures of my work very well" ($r(37.88) = .418, p = .042$). The question "over time one can become disconnected from this type of work" was statistically significantly correlated with "there are days I feel tired before I arrive at work" ($r(37.88) = .628, p = .001$). Also, a significant negative correlation was found

between "I always find new and interesting aspects of my work" and "after work I have enough energy for leisure activities" ($r(37.88) = -.465, p = .022$). The relationship between the ability to tolerate work well and the discovery of new and interesting aspects of work revealed a positive correlation, ($r(38.77) = 0.418, p = .042$), indicating a statistically significant association between these two variables. In the engagement subscale of the OLBI, higher scores indicate a higher level of disengagement from work. Therefore, the pre-intervention engagement score of 16.08 signifies low level of disengagement of the participants, and the post-intervention engagement score of 14.77 indicate the level of disengagement reported by participants before and after the intervention, respectively. A decrease in the disengagement scores post-intervention, from 16.08 to 14.77, would suggest a reduction in the reported level of disengagement. This reduction is generally considered positive, as it indicates that the intervention may have helped participants become less disengaged from their work (Appendix J).

OLBI Combined Subscales

Pre-and-post measurements were taken to gauge changes in burnout levels over the 6-week timeline of this project. Pre-subscale total results were 35.71 and post resulted in 33.27 (Appendix J). These numbers represent the mean scores on the combined subscales of engagement and exhaustion. These results validate that nurse leaders are, in fact, experiencing low to moderate levels of burnout. The scores fall within the range typically associated with moderate levels of burnout. A total score ranging from 33 to 48 was considered moderate burnout (Demerouti et al., 2010).

From the results, it appears that there has been a slight decrease in burnout levels from pre-to post-measurements. However, both combined scores still indicate moderate levels of burnout. This suggests that while there may have been some improvement, the overall level of

burnout among the respondents remains a concern and likely requires further intervention or support measures.

Qualitative Data Summary

Survey feedback in anonymous comments from participants was read and categorized into themes as appropriate. Feedback indicated that the Press Pause cards, acting as gentle prompts for mindful breaks, and the aromatherapy inhalers containing stress-relieving essential oils, were the most beneficial elements of the toolkit, promoting mental refreshment and decreasing feelings of burnout. Moreover, participants expressed in their comments that the mental health resources and information proved to be highly beneficial, with some indicating that they were previously unaware of these resources until they received the education and toolkit. Common themes emerged, such as the acknowledgment that "burnout for nurse leaders is real" and gratitude for addressing the issue of nurse leader burnout through the project. Additionally, participants conveyed appreciation for the guidance on reducing burnout and were thankful for the reassurance that they were not alone in their sentiments regarding their work. We lost one nurse leader due to voluntary termination during the project implementation phase.

Plan for Dissemination

This project will be the capstone for the project lead. The project will be presented as a podium and poster presentation as a requirement for graduation. In addition, the project will be disseminated at internal and/or external professional forums in poster, podium, or webinar formats or as a publication in a professional journal (Appendix Q).

Discussion

The findings of this project underscore the pervasive issue of burnout among nurse leaders, aligning with themes and contributing factors identified in the literature reviewed and supported by the PARHIS framework. Potential scores on each subscale when using a four-point scale range from 8 to 32 (10-40 on a five-point scale), with the total potential OLBI score ranging from 16 to 64 (20-80 on a five-point scale). Higher scores indicate higher levels of burnout (Demerouti et al., 2010). A total score on the four-point scale ranging from 16 to 32 for both subscales was considered low burnout while a total score ranging from 33 to 48 was considered moderate burnout and a total score ranging from 49 to 64 was considered high burnout. (Demerouti et al., 2010). A t-test was used to compare the means of the pre-and-post-survey results to determine if there was a statistically significant difference between them. It is suitable for situations where you have two groups and want to assess if the means of these groups are equal or different (Grove & Gray, 2019). Moderate correlations indicates that individuals who reported reduced cognitive engagement at work and mechanical task performance tended to experience increased disconnection from their work, suggesting a relationship between envisioning oneself solely in this type of work and experiencing feelings of being sickened by work tasks. Correlations were additionally identified indicating that nurse leaders may be experiencing elements of burnout, including exhaustion, decreased engagement, and a diminished sense of personal accomplishment. This suggests a delicate balance between the demands of a nurse leadership role and focus on personal well-being, highlighting the importance of addressing both aspects in mitigating burnout.

The descriptive statistics provide insights into the average scores for different questions on the OLBI survey before and after the implementation of the burnout mitigation toolkit. These

findings suggest that the burnout mitigation toolkit had a positive impact on aspects related to engagement in work, tolerance of work pressure, and perceiving work as a positive challenge (Appendix I). The findings align with existing literature emphasizing the significance of organizational factors in contributing to burnout among nurse leaders, further emphasizing the need for supportive work environments and effective leadership practices (Kelly et al., 2019).

Participants with higher levels of education, as indicated by their highest degree completed, tended to report feeling more engaged in their work. These findings indicate that there is a significant positive correlation between the highest level of degree completed and feeling more engaged in work. Additionally, participants with more years of experience in a nurse leader position tended to report thinking less at work and doing their job mechanically. These findings indicate that there is a significant positive correlation between years in a nurse leader position and thinking less at work. However, there was no significant relationship found between the highest level of degree completed and thinking less at work.

Each question in the exhaustion category taps into different aspects of this experience, such as feeling tired, fatigued, or strained because of work-related activities. By analyzing responses to these exhaustion-related questions, this project determined the degree to which individuals experience burnout due to prolonged exposure to work-related stressors. High scores on exhaustion items indicate a greater likelihood of burnout, whereas low scores suggest lower levels of burnout and greater resilience to work-related strain. As well, results suggest a strong connection between experiencing emotional exhaustion at work and conveying negative sentiments about one's job.

There were several variables that measured fatigue across various dimensions, the correlation of questions related to exhaustion in the OLBI reflects the interconnectedness of

feelings of fatigue, depletion, and strain experienced by individuals in relation to their work environment. This was conveyed by the negative correlations among participants who reported feeling sickened by their work tasks and sometimes also tended to feel worn out and weary after work. This suggests that participants who reported feeling emotionally drained during their work tended to feel more disconnected over time from their work and suggests that participants who reported finding new and interesting aspects in their work also tended to report fewer days of feeling tired before arriving at work.

High scores on engagement items indicate feelings of disconnection, detachment, and disengagement from work tasks, which are associated with higher levels of burnout and reduced job satisfaction. The correlation of questions related to engagement in the OLBI reflects the extent to which individuals experience a sense of dedication, absorption, and efficacy in their work, which serves as a protective factor against burnout. Participants reported feeling more engaged in their work, slightly improved tolerance of work pressure, and an increased perception of work as a positive challenge. Demonstrating that participants who reported seeing this type of work as the only option for themselves tended to have difficulty managing the amount of work. These findings suggest that there is a significant negative correlation between thinking less at work and finding work to be a positive challenge. These outcomes indicate a positive shift in participants' attitudes and experiences towards their work after the intervention.

The cost of nurse leader burnout was highlighted, encompassing both human and financial costs. Burnout not only impacts the health and well-being of nurse leaders but also results in decreased productivity, increased turnover rates, and potential negative implications for patient care and outcomes. These findings mirror those reported on in the literature. (Howell, et

L., 2020). It is imperative for healthcare organizations to invest in strategies to mitigate nurse leader burnout, recognizing it as a critical organizational and public health concern.

The impact of the project on additional measures like patient experience, nurse satisfaction, and nurse leader turnover remains to be established. Initial data from PSJMC in February 2023 indicated an overall patient experience of 71.14%, while at the project's completion in January 2024, the overall patient experience improved to 81.95% (Appendix E). During the course of the project, one nurse leader left the organization. Ongoing tracking of nurse leader turnover data is necessary to understand factors responsible for turnover and identify those activities that promote retention. Nurse satisfaction findings concerning burnout levels showed a rate of 38% in October 2022 and 37% in October 2023. The evaluation of the project's influence on these results is pending until the subsequent annual survey in October 2024 (Appendices C & D).

Recommendations

Based on these findings and evidence from the literature on the effects of COVID-19, strategies to alleviate nurse leader burnout include establishing comprehensive support programs, such as the IHI's "Framework for Improving Joy in Work", 2017. Additionally, cultivating a culture that prioritizes well-being and resilience, offering resources for stress management and self-care, and tackling organizational factors contributing to burnout. The positive outcomes observed from implementing the burnout mitigation toolkit in this project indicate that tailored interventions addressing the specific needs of nurse leaders can effectively mitigate burnout and improve overall well-being.

Looking ahead, ongoing commitment and efforts from healthcare organizations are vital to comprehensively address nurse leader burnout and foster a healthier and more sustainable

workforce. By making the mitigation of nurse leader burnout a priority, healthcare organizations can ensure that their staff members feel supported, motivated, and engaged in their roles while reducing the significant costs associated with nurse leader turnover. It is imperative for health systems to focus on implementing established strategies to alleviate nurse leadership burnout.

Implications for Change

The future nursing implications for change regarding a mitigation of burnout toolkit to decrease nurse leader burnout are multifaceted and critical for fostering a healthier work environment. Firstly, this project demonstrated the pressing need for healthcare organizations to prioritize the integration of burnout mitigation strategies into their leadership development programs. This includes incorporating training modules on stress management, resilience-building, and self-care practices tailored specifically for nurse leaders. Additionally, there should be a concerted effort to promote a culture of open communication and psychological safety within healthcare settings, where nurse leaders feel empowered to seek support and share their challenges without fear of stigma or repercussion.

Ongoing evaluation and refinement of the mitigation toolkit are essential to ensure its effectiveness and relevance in addressing the evolving needs of nurse leaders. This involves soliciting feedback from users, conducting regular assessments of burnout levels, and adapting interventions accordingly. Additionally, there is a need for further research to explore the long-term impact of the toolkit on nurse leader well-being, job satisfaction, and retention rates. Longitudinal studies can provide valuable insights into the sustainability of intervention efforts and inform future best practices in mitigating nurse leader burnout and potentially decreasing turnover.

By working together, healthcare organizations can develop targeted interventions that address both individual and systemic factors contributing to nurse leader burnout. Ultimately, investing in the well-being of nurse leaders not only benefits their own health and job satisfaction but also has ripple effects on the overall quality of patient care, patient experience, nurse satisfaction, turnover and overall organizational performance.

Limitations

The primary limitation of this DNP project pertained to the sample size. Initially, the sample comprised 25 inpatient nurse leaders, with 24 participating in the pre-survey; however, one leader resigned during the project. Of the remaining 24 nurse leaders, 22 completed the post-survey. A recommendation for improvement would be to increase the sample size, allowing for a more nuanced analysis based on roles and years of leadership experience, all while upholding confidentiality. Additionally, extending the study duration by another twelve weeks could provide further insights into the project's impact. Moreover, reassessing the study six months later would ascertain whether inpatient nurse leaders have sustained the use of the toolkit and continued positive trending to decreasing exhaustion and disengagement. While the toolkit demonstrated positive effects among nurse leaders, it is crucial to continue emphasizing well-being practices, enhancing nursing leader retention, and expanding resilience initiatives. However, it is worth noting that the truncated implementation and utilization period of the toolkit may have influenced the findings.

Conclusions

This paper explores the EBP project conducted by a DNP student, focusing on the implementation of a burnout mitigation toolkit for inpatient nurse leaders at PSJMC. The PICO question guiding this project was: "Does the utilization of a burnout mitigation toolkit effectively

support nurse leaders and decrease nurse leader burnout?" The findings from this project favorably answer this question. Despite the critical role of nurse leaders, burnout rates among them remain underexamined and poorly understood. Given the significance of their work, it is imperative to implement and investigate further strategies to comprehend the impact of burnout on nurse leaders comprehensively.

References

- Bergström, A., Ehrenberg, A., Eldh, A. C., Graham, I. D., Gustafsson, K., Harvey, G., Hunter, S., Kitson, A., Malone, J., & Wallin, L. (2020). The use of the PARIHS framework in implementation research and practice—a citation analysis of the literature. *Implementation Science, 15*, 1-51. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-020-01003-0>
- Boston-Fleischhauer, C. (2022). Reversing the great resignation in nursing: More things to consider. *Journal of Nursing Administration, 52*(6), 324-326. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NNA.0000000000001155>
- Bootland, D., Coughlan, E., Galloway, R., Goubet, S., & McWhirter, E. (2017). *Critical appraisal from papers to patient: A practical guide*. CRC Press.
- Danaci, E., & Koç, Z. (2020). The association of job satisfaction and burnout with individualized care perceptions in nurses. *Nursing Ethics, 27*(1), 301-315. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0969733019836151>
- Demerouti, E., Mostert, K., & Bakker, A. B. (2010). Burnout and work engagement: A thorough investigation of the independency of both constructs. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology, 15*(3), 209. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/a0019408>
- Demerouti, E., & Bakker, A. B. (2008). The Oldenburg Burnout Inventory: A good alternative to measure burnout and engagement. *Handbook of stress and burnout in health care, 65*(7).
- Grove, S., & Gray, J. (2019). *Understanding nursing research: Building an evidence-based practice* (7th ed.). Elsevier.
- Harvey, G., & Kitson, A. (2016). PARIHS revisited: From heuristic to integrated framework for the successful implementation of knowledge into practice. *Implementation Science, 11*(33), 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-016-0398-2>

- Harvey, G., McCormack, B., Kitson, A., Lynch, E., & Titchen, A. (2018). Designing and implementing two facilitation interventions within the 'Facilitating Implementation of Research Evidence (FIRE)' study: A qualitative analysis from an external facilitators' perspective. *Implementation Science*, 13(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-018-0812-z>
- Helfrich, C., Damschroder, L., Hagedorn, H., Daggett, G., Sahay, A., Ritchies, M., Damush, T., Guihan, M., Ulrich, P., & Streler, C. (2010). A critical synthesis of literature on the promoting action on research implementation in health services (PARIHS) framework. *Implementation Science*, 5(82). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-5-82>
- Howell, T. G., Mylod, D. E., Lee, T. H., Shanafelt, T., & Prissel, P. (2020). Physician burnout, resilience, and patient experience in a community practice: correlations and the central role of activation. *Journal of Patient Experience*, 7(6), 1491-1500. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2374373519888343>
- Kelly, L., Gee, P., & Butler, R. (2021). Impact of nurse burnout on organizational and position turnover. *Nursing Outlook*, 69(1), 96-102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.outlook.2020.06.008>
- Kelly, L., Lefton, C., & Fischer, S. (2019). Nurse leader burnout, satisfaction, and work-life balance. *The Journal of Nursing Administration*, 49(9), 404-410. <https://doi.org/10.1097/nna.0000000000000784>
- Kelly, L., & Adams, J. (2018) Nurse leader burnout: How to find your joy. *Nurse Leader*, 16(1), 24-28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mnl.2017.10.006>
- Kristensen H., Borg T, & Hounsgaard L. (2011). Facilitation of research-based evidence within occupational therapy in stroke rehabilitation. *British Journal of Occupational Therapy*. 74(10), 473-483. <https://doi.org/10.4276/030802211X13182481841949>

- Lisle, L., Speroni, K., Aroom, W., Crouch, L., & Honigsberg, H. (2020). Differences in compassion satisfaction, compassion fatigue, and work environment factors by hospital registered nurse type. *Online Journal of Issues in Nursing*, 25(3).
<https://doi.org/10.3912/OJIN.Vol25No03PPT44>
- Nundy, S., Cooper, L., & Mate., K. (2022). The quintuple aim for health care improvement: A new imperative to advance health equity. *JAMA*, 327(6),521–522.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2021.25181>
- Pate, A., Reed, B., Cain, J., & Schlesselman, L. (2023). Improving and expanding research on burnout and stress in the academy. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 87(1). <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe8907>
- Peacock, A. (2023). Compassion satisfaction, compassion fatigue, and vicarious trauma. *Nursing Management*, 54(1),14-22. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.numa.0000905000.95966.96>
- Perlo, J., Balik, B., Swensen, S., Kabcenell, A., Landsman, J., & Feeley, D. (2017). *IHI Framework for improving joy in work*. [White Paper]. Institute for Healthcare Improvement. <https://www.ihl.org/resources/Pages/IHIWhitePapers/Framework-Improving-Joy-in-Work.aspx>
- Prochnow, J., McGill, R., Pesut, D., Gordon, D., Deno, F. & Becknell, M. (2021). Challenges and choices: Insights derived from a survey of nurse leader burnout. *Nursing Management*, 52(10), 32-40. <https://doi:10.109701.NUMA.0000792012.90700.f2>
- Remegio, W., Rivera, R., Griffin, M., & Fitzpatrick, J. (2021). The professional quality of life and work engagement of nurse leaders. *Nurse Leader*, 19(1), 95–100.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mnl.2020.08.001>

- Sandström, B., Borglin, G., Nilsson, R., & Willman, A. (2011). Promoting the implementation of evidence-based practice: A literature review focusing on the role of nursing leadership. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 8(4), 212-223. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1741-6787.2011.00216.x>
- Seguin, C. (2019). A survey of nurse leaders to explore the relationship between grit and measures of success and well-being. *Journal of Nursing Administration*, 49(3), 125-131. <https://doi:10.1097/NNA.0000000000000725>
- Shah M., Gandrakota, N., Cimiotti, J., Ghose, N., Moore, M., & Ali, M. (2021). Prevalence of and factors associated with nurse burnout in the US. *JAMA Network Open*, 4(2), e2036469. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.36469>
- Stetler, C., Damschroder, L., Helfrich, C., Hildi, H. (2011). A guide for applying a revised version of the PARIHS framework for implementation. *Implementation Science*, 6(99). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-6-99>

Appendix A
DNP Project Timeline

<p>-PSJMC Research & EBP Council approval</p>	<p>- Providence IRB submission</p> <p>-California State University, Los Angeles IRB submission</p> <p>- Providence IRB approval</p>	<p>-California State University, Los Angeles IRB approval</p>	<p>-Providence Willis Tower Watson caregiver annual survey</p> <p>-OLBI burnout assessment (Pre) survey</p> <p>- Implementation of nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit</p>	<p>- OLBI burnout assessment (Post) survey</p>	<p>-Result data collection and analysis</p>
---	---	---	--	--	---

Appendix B

Evaluation Methods

Variable Name (Definition)	Pre- Implementation Baseline	Post- Implementation	Source	How it will be measured	Why used in project	How it will be analyzed
Nurse leader burnout OLBI survey questionnaire	X	X	OLBI Burnout survey questionnaire (Appendix H)	OLBI survey questionnaire results	Outcome measure	Utilize SPSS to compare pre-and -post toolkit implementation survey results
PSJMC Nurse satisfaction	X	X	Providence WTW caregiver survey (Appendices C &D)	Providence WTW caregiver survey results	Outcome measure	Compare pre- and-post implementation survey results
PSJMC Patient experience	X	X	Providence Press Ganey patient satisfaction survey (Appendix E)	Providence Press Ganey patient satisfaction survey results trending	Outcome measure	Compare-pre and-post implementation survey results

Appendix C

PSJMC Nurse Satisfaction (October 2022 Baseline)

Category	7510 ST. JUDE MEDICAL CENTER	vs. 2021 Providence Caregiver Experience Survey HISTORICALS	vs. SOUTHERN CA OCHD	vs. US Healthcare Norm
Sustainable Engagement Segmentation	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sustainable Engagement	83	-1	+4 *	+8 *
Caregiver Resonance with the Mission	86	+1	+7 *	N/A
Mission & Values	89	0	+5 *	+8 *
Intent to Stay	83	-6 *	+3 *	+2
Community	86	-2	+3 *	+8 *
Role Success	86	0	+3 *	+10 *
Burnout	38	-4 *	+1	+3 *
Workload	61	+1	+4 *	+1

Appendix D

PSJMC Nurse Satisfaction (October 2023)

Benchmarks

Total Favorable Scores

Category	7510 ST. JUDE MEDICAL CENTER	vs. 2022 Providence Caregiver Experience Survey Historicals	vs. SCA - SOUTHERN CA OCHD	vs. US Healthcare Norm
Sustainable Engagement Segmentation	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Sustainable Engagement	85	+2	+6 *	+13 *
Caregiver Resonance with the Mission	87	0	+7 *	N/A
Mission & Values	91	+1	+5 *	+8 *
Intent to Stay	86	+1	+4 *	+7 *
Role Success	88	+1	+4 *	+12 *
Community	87	+1	+4 *	+7 *
Senior Leadership	80	+1	+10 *	+14 *
Supervision	83	0	+3 *	+3 *
Burnout	37	-2	+1	+2
Workload	68	+6 *	+7 *	+9 *
Empowerment	83	0	+4 *	+5 *
Quality	91	0	+3 *	+8 *
Respect	82	-1	+4 *	+12 *

*Statistically Significant

■ You are below benchmark

■ You are above benchmark

Appendix E PSJMC Patient Experience

Pre
71.14%

Post
81.95%

Appendix F

Figure 1. PARIHS Framework

Figure 1. Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (PARIHS) Framework (Kristensen, Borg & Hounsgaard, 2011)

Appendix G

Figure 2. Modified PARIHS Framework

Figure 2. Modified PARIHS Framework used for this EBP Project

Appendix H

OLBI Survey Questionnaire

Mitigation of Nurse Leader Burnout- Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (2)

To Project Participant:

You are invited to take part in an evidenced-based project conducted by Dawn Price MSN, NE-BC, RNC-OB, C-EFM, student at California State University, Los Angeles and her faculty chair, Elizabeth Winokur, PhD, RN. In this project, we hope to learn more about nurse leader's burnout. You were selected to participate in this project because of your experience as an actively working nurse leader. We hope that our project will lead to understanding how to mitigate nurse leader burnout.

Participants will be expected to participate in an online survey which will be emailed. The entire survey should take approximately 10 minutes to complete. The first part of the survey consists of demographic related questions and the second part of the survey is Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI) version 5 scale. You may skip any question that you do not wish to answer.

There is only minimal risk to this project, including the loss of anonymity as well as the potential for some distress to arise as participants answer the questionnaire as some of the questions ask to recall stressful conditions at work. To reduce the risk, no email addresses or identifying information will be sought or collected for this project. For any distress you may find from question, you may skip any question that you do not wish to answer.

Reports resulting from this project will not identify you as a participant. All information gathered in this study will remain confidential, only aggregated, de-identified information will be reported.

If you have any questions about this project at any time, please call Elizabeth Winokur, PhD, RN, CEN at 714-402-4270 or write her at ewinok2@calstatela.edu or 5151 State University Dr, Los Angeles, CA 90032. You may also contact Dawn Price the Co-PI at 714-469-2318 or at DawnPrice@csu.fullerton.edu

By participating in this evidenced-based project, you indicate that you have read the form and agree voluntarily to participate. If you choose not to take part, there will be no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are entitled. If you agree to take part, you are free to withdraw from it at any time. Likewise, no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled will occur.

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

* Required

1. I always find new and interesting aspects in my work.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree
I always find new and interesting aspects in my work.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

2. There are days when I feel tired before I arrive at work

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree
There are days when I feel tired before I arrive at work.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

3. It happens more and more often that I talk about my work in a negative way.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree
It happens more and more often that I talk about my work in a negative way.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

4. After work, I tend to need more time than in the past in order to relax and feel better

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree
After work, I tend to need more time than in the past in order to relax and feel better.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

5. I can tolerate the pressure of my work very well

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree
I can tolerate the pressure of my work very well	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

6. Lately, I tend to think less at work and do my job almost mechanically

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree
Lately, I tend to think less at work and do my job almost mechanically	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

7. I find my work to be a positive challenge.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree
I find my work to be a positive challenge	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

8. During my work, I often feel emotionally drained.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree
During my work, I often feel emotionally drained	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

9. Over time, one can become dis-connected from this type of work

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree
Over time, one can become dis-connected from this type of work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

10. After working, I have enough energy for my leisure activities

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree
After working, I have enough energy for my leisure activities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

11. Sometimes I feel sickened by my work tasks

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree
Sometimes I feel sickened by my work tasks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

12. After my work, I usually feel worn out and weary

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree
After my work, I usually feel worn out and weary	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	

13. This is the only type of work that I can imagine myself doing.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree
This is the only type of work that I can imagine myself doing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

14. Usually, I can manage the amount of my work well.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree
Usually, I can manage the amount of my work well	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

15. I feel more and more engaged in my work

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree n
I feel more and more engaged in my work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

16. When I work, I usually feel energized.

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor dis
When I work, I usually feel energized	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

17. How many years have you been in a Nurse Leader position?

	1-5	6-10	11-15	16-20	20 +
How many years have you been in a Nurse Leader position?	<input type="radio"/>				

18. What is the highest-level degree completed?

	ADN	BSN	MSN or higher	Other
What is the highest-level degree completed?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Statement 2	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

19. Are you certified as a Nurse Leader?

Yes

No

Appendix I

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics OLBI Pre-Post Mean Average and p-value

Question	Pre-survey Mean N=24	Post-survey Mean N=22	p-value
#1 I always find new and interesting aspects work.	4.00	4.18	.199
#2 There are days when I feel tired before I arrive at work.	4.13	3.84	.214
#3 It happens more and more that I talk about my work in a negative way.	2.79	2.55	.416
#4 After work, I tend to need more time than in the past to relax and feel better.	3.46	3.09	.257
#5 I can tolerate the pressure of my work very well.	3.50	3.59	.733
#6 Lately, I tend to think less at work, do my job mechanically.	2.38	2.23	.609
# 7 I find my work to be a positive challenge.	4.04	4.23	.117
#8 During my work, I often feel emotionally drained	3.13	3.05	.836
#9 Over time, one can become disconnected form this type of work.	3.00	3.27	.402
#10 After working, I have enough energy for my leisure activities.	2.63	3.23	.091
#11 Sometimes I feel sickened by my work tasks.	2.63	2.41	.516
#12 After work, I usually feel worn out and weary.	3.38	3.41	.903
#13 This is the only type of work that I can imagine myself doing	3.13	3.79	.031*
#14 Usually, I can manage the amount of work well.	3.79	3.77	.942
#15 I feel more and more engaged in my work.	3.58	3.91	.106
#16 When I work, I usually feel energized.	3.48	3.68	.351

Note. p-value calculated on a four-point Likert-like scale.

*Significant at <0.05

Appendix J

Table 2. OLBI Subscales Pre-Post Survey (4-Point Scale)

Engagement	Pre	Post
#1 I always find new and interesting aspects work.	1.96	1.82
#3 It happens more and more that I talk about my work in a negative way.	2.79	2.55
#6 Lately, I tend to think less at work, do my job mechanically.	2.38	2.50
# 7 I find my work to be a positive challenge.	1.96	1.77
#9 Over time, one can become dis-connected form this type of work.	3.00	3.18
#11 Sometimes I feel sickened by my work tasks.	2.67	2.32
#13 This is the only type of work that I can imagine myself doing	2.83	2.23
#15 I feel more and more engaged in my work.	2.42	2.09
TOTAL	20.01	18.46
x0.08 (4-point scale) =	16.08	14.77

Exhaustion	Pre	Post
#2 There are days when I feel tired before I arrive at work.	4.08	3.86
#4 After work, I tend to need more time than in the past to relax and feel better.	3.38	3.09
#5 I can tolerate the pressure of my work very well.	2.50	2.36
#8 During my work, I often feel emotionally drained	3.13	3.14
#10 After working, I have enough energy for my leisure activities.	3.38	2.77
#12 After work, I usually feel worn out and weary.	2.21	3.41
#14 Usually, I can manage the amount of work well.	2.48	2.23
#15 I feel more and more engaged in my work.	2.48	2.27
TOTAL	24.54	23.13
x0.08 (4-point scale) =	19.63	18.50

OLBI Combined Subscales

	Pre	Post
Combined Subscale TOTAL	35.71	33.27

Appendix K

Table 3. Correlations Spearman's Rho OLBI Post Survey

Engagement	Years in a nurse leader position	Highest level of degree
#1 I always find new and interesting aspects work.	.714	.394
#3 It happens more and more that I talk about my work in a negative way.	.904	.860
#6 Lately, I tend to think less at work, do my job mechanically.	.046*	.718
# 7 I find my work to be a positive challenge.	.456	.910
#9 Over time, one can become dis-connected form this type of work.	.780	.601
#11 Sometimes I feel sickened by my work tasks.	.099+	.152
#13 This is the only type of work that I can imagine myself doing	.776	.765
#15 I feel more and more engaged in my work.	.168	.297
Exhaustion		
#2 There are days when I feel tired before I arrive at work.	.937	.170
#4 After work, I tend to need more time than in the past to relax and feel better.	.247	.188
#5 I can tolerate the pressure of my work very well.	.821	.822
#8 During my work, I often feel emotionally drained	.516	.437
#10 After working, I have enough energy for my leisure activities.	.529	.646
#12 After work, I usually feel worn out and weary.	.766	.714
#14 Usually, I can manage the amount of work well.	.075+	.695
#16 When I work, I usually feel energized.		.221

Note. Spearman rho. *Correlation is significant at $< .05$, +Correlation is moderate at $.05$.

Appendix L

Table 4. Participant Demographics

Years in Nurse Leader Position	Participants
1-5	10
6-10	6
11-15	6
16-20	1
20+	1
Highest Degree	Participants
ADN	0
BSN	6
MSN or Higher	18
Other	0

Appendix M

OLBI Survey Use Permission Approval

CCC RightsLink Home ? Help Live Chat Sign In Create Account

The job demands-resources model of burnout.

Author: Demerouti, Evangelia; Bakker, Arnold B.; Nachreiner, Friedhelm; Schaufeli, Wilmar B.
Publication: Journal of Applied Psychology
Publisher: American Psychological Association
Date: Jun 1, 2001
Copyright © 2001, American Psychological Association

Quick Price Estimate

I would like to...	republish in a thesis/dissertation	With minor editing privileges...	no
Describe who will republish the content (person or entity)...	Academic institution	In the following language(s)...	Original language of publication
I would like to use...	Measure, scale or instrument	With incidental promotional use...	no
I want rights for...	Main product	The lifetime unit quantity of new product...	0 to 499
My format is...	<input type="checkbox"/> Print <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Electronic	My currency is...	USD - \$
Duration of use...	life of current edition	Quick Price	Click Quick Price
Creation of copies for the disabled...	no	<input type="button" value="QUICK PRICE"/> <input type="button" value="CONTINUE"/>	

Note: It is the requestor's responsibility to determine whether a copyright and/or credit notice to a third-party owner appears near an item. Permission to use any third-party material published by American Psychological Association must be obtained from the third-party owner. American Psychological Association disclaims any responsibility for any use you make of content owned by third parties without their permission.

CCC RightsLink Home ? Help Live Chat Dawn Price

The job demands-resources model of burnout.

Author: Demerouti, Evangelia; Bakker, Arnold B.; Nachreiner, Friedhelm; Schaufeli, Wilmar B.
Publication: Journal of Applied Psychology
Publisher: American Psychological Association
Date: Jun 1, 2001
Copyright © 2001, American Psychological Association

Order Completed

Thank you for your order.

This Agreement between California State University Fullerton -- Dawn Price ("You") and American Psychological Association ("American Psychological Association") consists of your license details and the terms and conditions provided by American Psychological Association and Copyright Clearance Center.

Your confirmation email will contain your order number for future reference.

License Number	5596230011292	Printable Details
License date	Jul 25, 2023	

Licensed Content	Order Details
Licensed Content Publisher	Type of use
Licensed Content Publication	Requestor type
Licensed Content Title	Format
Licensed copyright line	Portion
Licensed Content Author	Rights for
Licensed Content Date	Duration of use
Licensed Content Volume	Creation of copies for the disabled
Licensed Content issue	With minor editing privileges
	In the following language(s)
	With incidental promotional use
	Lifetime unit quantity of new product

Appendix N

Institutional DNP Project Approval Letter

Institutional DNP Project Approval Letter

May 1, 2023

This letter is to show that, I Julie Kim as the CNO of Providence St Jude Medical Center give permission to Dawn Price RN to conduct the project titled- Mitigation of Nurse Leader Burnout at Providence St Jude Medical Center.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Providence St Jude Nursing Research Council, and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project lead is allowed to: Create a nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit and conduct a pre and post-toolkit implementation burnout assessment survey. With a project goal to reduce nurse leader burnout by 3%.

- (1) collect data pre and post OLBI Burnout Assessment Survey Data
- (2) access necessary documents/data
- (3) conduct necessary interactions with staff relevant to their project
- (4) distribute the OLBI Burnout Assessment Survey to Nurse Leaders using the staff email

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations at Providence St Jude Medical Center and its covered entities.

Signature:

Name: Julie Kim MSN, RN, CMSRN, NE-BC

Title: Chief Nurse Officer

Contact Information: 714-992-3000

Appendix O

Providence IRB Clinical Inquiry Project-Not Research Determination

CLINICAL INQUIRY PROJECT – NOT RESEARCH DETERMINATION

July 17, 2023

Dear [Dawn Price](#):

On 7/17/2023, the Human Research Protection Program (HRPP) reviewed the following submission:

Title:	Mitigation of Nurse Leader Burnout
Project ID:	STUDY2023000360
Project Lead Name:	Dawn Price
Funding Source:	None

The HRPP determined that this project, as submitted, does not meet the definition of research as defined in the federal regulations, and does not require IRB review. This determination is based only upon the information submitted.

The project may proceed as described in the documents submitted for review and in line with requirements listed below and on the next page.

This determination does not exempt you from following hospital policies and procedures as they relate to conduct of this project.

As the project was deemed not to be research, any presentations or publications discussing the project may not refer to it as a research study or state that the project received IRB approval, but rather refer to it as a Quality Improvement project, Evidence-Based Practice project, etc.

Should there be any questions, please contact the HRPP at: PSJHIRBDetermination@providence.org

Appendix P

California State University, Los Angeles-IRB Approval

From: Claire Riner <no-reply@irbnet.org>

Sent: Tuesday, September 26, 2023 1:18 PM

To: Price, Dawn <DawnPrice@csu.fullerton.edu>; Elizabeth Winokur <ewinoku2@calstatela.edu>

Subject: [External] IRBNet Board Action

External Email Use Caution and Confirm Sender

Please note that California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has taken the following action on IRBNet:

Project Title: [2083723-1] Mitigation of Nurse Leader Burnout

Principal Investigator: Elizabeth Winokur, PhD

Submission Type: New Project

Date Submitted: July 25, 2023

Action: APPROVED

Effective Date: September 26, 2023

Review Type: Exempt Review

Should you have any questions you may contact Claire Riner at irb@calstatela.edu.

Thank you,
The IRBNet Support Team

Appendix Q

Western Institute of Nursing Conference Abstract

CSULA 15th Annual Evidenced-Based Practice Nursing Forum Abstract

CSUF Sigma Upsilon Beta International Induction Ceremony and Poster Session Abstract

MITIGATION OF NURSE LEADER BURNOUT

Dawn Price MSN, RN, NE-BC, RNC-OB, C-EFM

Elizabeth J. Winokur PhD, RN, CEN and Shauna Pearce DNP, MAOM, RN, HACP

California State University, Fullerton and California State University, Los Angeles

Purpose/Objectives: The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to create a nurse leader burnout mitigation toolkit and assess efficacy through a pre-and post-toolkit implementation burnout assessment survey at a community, Magnet[®]-recognized acute care hospital.

Background: Burnout is a substantial problem in healthcare and is identified as a significant cause of nurses leaving the nursing profession. Defined as a state of continuous psychological stress within work life, burnout has an influential negative impact on patients, the workforce, and organizations. The challenges in the current healthcare work environment create conditions for professional burnout at all nursing levels. Burnout for clinical nurses at the bedside is well researched, but there is growing need to investigate burnout of nurse leaders. Burnout resulting in increased turnover of nurse leaders impacts direct and indirect costs such as decreased care quality, patient satisfaction, and caregiver experience as well as the financial implications of recruiting and training new nurse leaders.

Methodology: This DNP project utilized the PARIHS conceptual framework to guide the implementation of an evidenced-based burnout mitigation toolkit. The mitigation of nurse leader burnout toolkit included a validated assessment tool, comprehensive education and training, support systems, workplace adjustments, and evaluation. Education and training provided nurse leaders with the knowledge and skills to identify symptoms of burnout and effectively manage stress. A list of available support resources was provided with the toolkit. This project utilized the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI) self-report assessment survey which measures burnout in the workplace. The pre survey assessment was completed and the following week, the mitigation of burnout toolkit was launched. The education sessions were completed, and mitigation of burnout toolkits were utilized by participants for a total of four weeks, then the post survey was completed. A comprehensive data analysis and evaluation were conducted to measure the effectiveness of the toolkit and identify areas for improvement.

Results: Results from the pre-and-post surveys demonstrate trending in the correct direction, indicating less burnout, but no statistically significant results were found. The data indicates that nurse leaders are feeling emotionally drained, tired and have difficulty tolerating the pressures of work. The results imply burnout among nurse leaders may be influenced by various factors such as workload, organizational culture, and job demands. Additionally, findings indicate that aspects of their work, such as incorporating innovative practices, professional development opportunities, or engaging in meaningful projects, support nurse leader well-being and help to mitigate nurse leader burnout.

Discussion and Nursing Implications: Findings from this project demonstrate the extent of burnout amongst nurse leaders and promising results from the use of the mitigation of burnout toolkit. However, the abbreviated timeframe for implementation and utilization of the toolkit may have impacted findings. Burnout rates of nurse leaders are not well studied or well understood. Since the work of nurse leaders is of utmost importance, further strategies must be implemented and investigated to determine the impact of burnout on nurse leaders.